

Organizational Support to the U.S. Arctic Science Program
Cooperative Agreement PLR0618885

Supplement Request: Summary of Proposed Work

1. INFORMATION & OUTREACH

ARCUS serves as a communication channel, providing information about research activities and arctic issues to the scientific community, agencies, and the public. The open and timely exchange of high-quality information is critical to the success of arctic science and education programs and to foster collaborations (National Research Council, 1993); this is especially true for the widely dispersed and multi-disciplinary arctic research and education communities. To be effective, broad dissemination of information must be accomplished through several methods and avenues:

1.1. Email Lists – ARCUS will continue developing and maintaining **ArcticInfo**, the primary email list for the arctic research community with over 6,800 subscribers. ArcticInfo provides timely information about funding opportunities, important events, publications, position announcements, and other news. Management of the email list is time-intensive as the announcements are fully “curated” and require understanding of arctic research issues as well as excellent editorial skills. All postings are archived in a searchable directory on the ARCUS website. ARCUS will further develop ArcticInfo by improving the digest functions and the search functionality in archived messages. In addition to ArcticInfo, ARCUS will continue to manage other email lists for the research community, including a **Polar Education Email List** (over 800 subscribers), which is an active discussion list focused on science-education issues, and program-focused lists, such as the Bering Ecosystem Study projects email list. ARCUS can also easily accommodate requests by the arctic research and education communities to manage additional email lists, as needed.

1.2. Witness the Arctic – ARCUS will publish the winter 2014 issue and begin work on the spring 2014 issue of the online *Witness the Arctic* newsletter. *Witness the Arctic* covers a broad spectrum of topics, including stories on major research initiatives and programs, arctic policy matters, science education activities, and interviews of agency program directors and other leaders. *Witness* articles will continue to focus on content that cannot be found through other venues.

1.3. Publication Directory – Work will be initiated on development of an online “publication directory” of science planning documents such as workshop reports, community recommendations, and white papers. There are many science planning documents that detail priorities and recommendations from the science community and agencies, yet it is currently very difficult to know about or find these plans. Therefore, there is a risk that subsequent planning exercises “re-invent the wheel” and fail to build on previous efforts. An online publications directory database would house metadata for science planning documents and provide a web link or downloadable file. A user could browse or search by fields such as keywords/topics, agencies, or programs. The publication directory would be populated with all

of the planning documents ARCUS currently hosts and those available through other arctic organizations and programs.

1.4. Arctic Calendar – The Arctic Calendar will continue to be maintained. The Calendar provides a “one-stop-shop” for information on arctic-related meetings, conferences, deadlines, and other events. Events can be browsed and searched through the Calendar webpage and are also available as RSS and iCal feeds. Calendar events are submitted by members of the research community through an easy online form and are also entered by ARCUS staff.

1.5. Web Portal – The ARCUS website and web portal will continue to be developed as an integrated, topically-based portal for arctic science, education, and outreach resources.

1.6. General Info and Outreach – In addition to the above activities, ARCUS is daily called on informally to provide information about arctic research efforts and resources. We frequently provide information to researchers, educators, and stakeholders on important findings and issues that they would not have received through normal institutional or disciplinary channels. Funding is also requested to manage a community outreach activity for the Arctic Observing Network; this activity involves providing members of the research community small levels of support for teleconferences, webinars, and other discussions (see: <http://www.arcus.org/search-program/aon/discussion-funding-form>).

2. NETWORKING

Networking—essentially facilitating connections between people, groups, and efforts—is a core function of ARCUS and an integral part of successful endeavors in this complex arctic science and education environment (Vorosmarty et al., 2007). A guiding principle in all ARCUS networking activities is to ensure that new activities and connections build on existing efforts and established programs. In addition, ARCUS focuses on *strategic* networking, where connections between people or groups serve a specific purpose in addition to providing the value inherent in cooperative activities.

2.1. Community Meeting Rooms – ARCUS proposes to continue hosting an “AGU Community Meeting Room” at the annual AGU Fall Meeting to encourage scientific collaboration and to make face-to-face meetings of opportunity possible for the arctic research community. Funds are included to begin planning for the 2014 meeting room activities and for final payment of the previous meeting room costs.

2.2. Directory of Arctic Researchers – The Directory currently holds the names, addresses, and science specialties of over 4,000 arctic researchers. The results of Directory user survey ARCUS administered in 2012 provided data indicating that it is used by agency personnel to find reviewers, by media to find expert opinions, and by scientists to find collaborators. ARCUS will develop improvements to the Directory, including an update of existing data. An increased outreach component will also make the community more aware of the Directory, and it will be updated on an annual basis by asking those in the Directory to check the accuracy of their information, and announcing an invitation for new researchers to join the Directory.

2.3. Travel Support

ARCUS proposes to provide minor travel support (1 travel slot) for an ARCUS staff member to travel to a major arctic conference for networking purposes.

3. CAPACITY BUILDING

Capacity building in the context of ARCUS' activities can be defined as enhancing people's knowledge and skills to meet current and emerging needs in arctic science and education. Several reports from the science community have called for capacity building activities, particularly focused on cross-disciplinary training (e.g., Walsh et al., 2011).

3.1. Arctic Visiting Speakers “Scientist Exchange” Program – ARCUS proposes a one-week “scientist exchange program.” This Scientist Exchange program will provide small travel grants for arctic scientists to invite experts outside their own field to travel to their institution and share knowledge, with the ultimate goal to increase collaboration and stimulate crosscutting ideas. For example, a researcher who works on coupled arctic system models may invite a non-arctic expert on complex systems modeling to visit his/her institution, give a series of presentations, and discuss new ideas in system modeling. This new program would be supported at a modest level with a target of four exchanges per year, and would be managed through an application process. One exchange would be supported through this supplement request.

3.2. Webinar Series – A small webinar series (starting with 2-4 webinars per year) will provide a cost-effective way to develop capacity and share expertise among the arctic science community. The webinar series will be developed with input from the science community (i.e., through a call for topic ideas via the ArcticInfo mailing list). Topics could range, for example, from new methodologies in observing platforms to the latest findings in arctic marine mammal ecology. This webinar series would be similar to seminars commonly provided at university departments, but would transfer that model to a format that is open and free to anyone who would like to join. Selected speakers and experts will provide the content for the webinars, while ARCUS will provide all organizational, logistics, and technical support. Funding requested in this supplement request will be used to develop this program.

4. INCREASE STAKEHOLDER INVOLVEMENT

Several groups and community reports have recognized the need to include stakeholders as part of the scientific planning process (e.g., Walsh et al., 2011; Canada-U.S. Northern Oil and Gas Research Forum Organizing Committee, 2011). Stakeholder involvement in the scientific process is critical both to ensure that scientific data and information meet decision maker needs, and also to generally broaden participation in arctic science. The definition of stakeholder varies depending on the issue, but can include resource managers, arctic residents, industry, and others. ARCUS proposes two small tasks to facilitate the integration of stakeholders in arctic science. Additional stakeholder-focused projects could be proposed in the future, building on the activities below and those that may be in development by other groups.

4.1. Sea Ice for Walrus Outlook – ARCUS will continue activities for the Sea Ice for Walrus Outlook (SIWO), which provides weekly reports from April through June on weather and sea ice

conditions in the Northern Bering Sea and southern Chukchi Sea regions of Alaska. As one of several partners in this project, ARCUS will continue the following tasks for the weekly reports: coordinate with the National Weather Service and NOAA to gather forecast data; work with local community members to incorporate local observations; edit report content and post online; announce the availability of the reports through several venues; and update the Sea Ice for Walrus Outlook Facebook page and respond to comments. Expansion of Sea Ice for Walrus Outlook activities in the future will be pursued through other funding means. Funds in this supplement request will be used to prepare for launching the SIWO season in April.

In addition, ARCUS staff will focus on increasing integration of stakeholder participation into all other cooperative agreement activities.

5. SUPPORT FOR THE AGENCY ARCTIC RESEARCH POLICY COMMITTEE

The U.S. Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC), chaired by the Director of the National Science Foundation, consists of agencies, departments, and offices across the Federal government and has convened interagency Implementation Teams to carry out its goals. ARCUS proposes to continue to provide support to IARPC, as summarized below and in the detail budget.

IARPC Secretariat Staffing

- Full time IARPC Executive Secretary (Sara Bowden, funded through a Professional Services Agreement). The primary responsibility of the Executive Secretary is to provide support to the IARPC Executive Director. The Secretary will be responsible for planning, recording, and posting meeting notes for all IARPC principals' and staff group meetings, and will be responsible for providing support in the implementation of the IARPC five-year plan and other IARPC tasks. This position is supervised by the IARPC Executive Director. Funding is requested to support this position through April 2014.
- Half-time Implementation Scientist/Consultant (Sandra Starkweather). This position ensures that goals of the IARPC research plan are being met and that collaboration with other entities, including state and local government agencies, NGO's, Indigenous groups, and academics is being promoted. In addition, this position will help develop the content for the IARPC website and provide input to IARPC outreach activities. This position is supervised by the IARPC Executive Director. Funding is requested to support this position through April 2014.

IARPC Secretariat Travel and Office/Communications Expenses

- Travel: One trip for either the IARPC Implementation Scientist (S. Starkweather) to travel to Washington, DC to meet with other IARPC staff and key Implementation Team members or for the Executive Secretary (S. Bowden) to travel to Alaska to meet with various stakeholder groups.
- Other Secretariat expenses: Includes office supplies, software upgrades and email group services, WebEx subscription, teleconference fees (through the existing ARCUS teleconferencing service), printing, and shipping outreach materials (e.g. IARPC brochure).

Website Consultants

Within the previous Cooperative Agreement, ARCUS contracted with Webitects, Inc. (<http://www.webitects.com/>) for Phases 1 (user research) and 2 (prototyping, currently underway) of a four-phase development for an IARPC website. Funding for an initial part of Phases 3 is requested to continue development and rollout of a website that provides updates on IARPC activities and facilitates conversations across agency and disciplinary boundaries, especially those within and between IARPC Implementation Teams.

ARCUS Staffing

Minor ARCUS staff time is requested for support of IARPC Secretariat activities (e.g., preparation of materials for meetings), oversight of website development work and contract, IARPC webinar organization and support, facilitating linkages and outreach with the broader (non-federal) research communities, and in assisting with the overall IARPC communications strategy.

6. NSF RESEARCH SUPPORT AND LOGISTICS

The NSF Research Support and Logistics (RSL) program supports the field component of research projects funded through science programs in the Division of Arctic Sciences and through other programs at NSF. With support from RSL, ARCUS has coordinated several planning processes that provide guidance from the research community to the agencies conducting research in the Arctic, with two resulting reports with recommendations for logistics needs (Schlosser et al., 1997; Schlosser et al., 2003). Since the last report in 2003, the scientific landscape has evolved considerably. As such, with guidance from the NSF RSL program, ARCUS will organize a workshop that gathers representatives of the science community and agencies to discuss current and emerging science needs, and how the RSL program can position itself to respond to those needs. The workshop will be held as a three-day meeting of approximately 50 participants, with a mix of plenary discussions and breakout groups. ARCUS will work with NSF to: provide overall organization of the workshop; select and invite participants; develop the workshop structure and agenda; develop and maintain webpages; provide on-site staff support, including web-streaming; support participant travel; and develop a workshop report.

In addition, staff time is requested to begin development of a report for a workshop held on Arctic Field Safety and Risk Management, and for minor support activities for the Study of Environmental Arctic Change (SEARCH).

7. OPERATIONS

The current ARCUS-NSF cooperative agreement budget includes a category called Core Support that funds program activities that simultaneously support multiple cooperative agreement tasks and cannot be attributed to a specific project. These costs are distinguished from indirect costs because they directly relate to programmatic activities rather than to the administrative infrastructure. The inclusion of funds that are not specific to particular projects or activities adds

stability to the operation of the organization and the staff team as well as providing crucial support that addresses multiple activities:

- Salaries and benefits of the Director of Programs for program management and oversight, when not dedicated to one specific activity or project;
- Salaries and benefits for the Systems Administrator for the portion of time spent developing or supporting capabilities required by multiple cooperative agreement activities and not dedicated to a specific activity or project;
- A small amount of salaries and benefits of other staff time for time dedicated to activities that cross all cooperative agreement categories.
- Staff travel to conferences and meetings to maintain and improve knowledge of arctic science and education issues or professional development, when this participation is not specific to one cooperative agreement activity (a total of 1 travel slot)
- Hardware and software technology to provide particular system or technical capability required of multiple cooperative agreement activities.